

An examination of the efficacy of treatment for posttraumatic stress disorder in combat veterans

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Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) remains one of the most prevalent and debilitating psychological conditions among combat veterans. This literature review critically examines the efficacy of established and emerging treatments, focusing on this population's complex and evolving needs. Trauma-focused therapies, such as cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT) and eye movement desensitisation and reprocessing (EMDR), demonstrate strong short-term outcomes; however, their long-term effectiveness and accessibility are often inconsistent, particularly for underrepresented groups. Many existing studies utilise small, homogeneous samples, which limits the applicability of findings to women, racial and ethnic minorities, and LGBTQ+ veterans. This review underscores the necessity for inclusive research and integrative care models that amalgamate evidence-based treatments with complementary approaches, including mindfulness, yoga, and digital interventions. Persistent barriers (such as stigma, systemic inequity, and logistical constraints) continue to hinder engagement and recovery. The review advocates for a culturally responsive framework emphasising symptom reduction, identity, community connection, and long-term well-being. Future research must prioritise diversity in study samples and examine the sustained impact of both conventional and holistic modalities. Building an inclusive and veteran-informed treatment landscape is vital to addressing the full extent of PTSD within combat-affected populations.

Keywords: combat veterans; integrative care; posttraumatic stress disorder; trauma-focused therapy; treatment accessibility

Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) is a chronic and debilitating condition often experienced by combat veterans. While treatment has traditionally focused on symptom reduction, increasing evidence suggests that a more comprehensive approach is necessary: one that considers the broader psychosocial context of veterans' lives. This literature review critically examines current treatment models, explores gaps in care, and identifies the need for more inclusive and accessible solutions.

PTSD is a mental disorder that disproportionately affects servicemen and women who have been in combat. Combat veterans diagnosed with PTSD have poorer treatment outcomes than their civilian counterparts diagnosed with PTSD (Beidel et al., 2017). These outcomes result from a lack of research and literature on evidence-based treatments, treatment effectiveness over extended periods, and treatment effectiveness since the classification change of PTSD in the DSM-5. Current studies on PTSD treatments have shown minimal benefits, with even fewer veterans achieving full remission (Beidel et al., 2017). Even when treatments reduce the severity of PTSD symptoms, the symptoms remain a concern.

The prevalence of PTSD has dramatically increased over the last 10 years, approaching 20% among combat veterans. Less than 10% of those veterans who begin therapy complete their treatment. Given these factors, it is crucial to provide empirically supported and effective treatment (Jackson et al., 2019). PTSD affects veterans not only mentally but also physically and emotionally. Although PTSD is detrimental to individuals, it also has lasting effects on their loved ones in the form of secondary traumatization. These loved ones are more frequently diagnosed with depression and anxiety, regardless of the severity of the combat veteran's symptoms. Secondary trauma refers to the transference of symptoms from individuals who are directly traumatised to those who are close to them (Zerach, 2015). PTSD is not something that will fade over time; rather, it is an experience that veterans must learn to adjust to and cope with for the rest of their lives. Their mental health creates a ripple effect not only on their loved ones but also on the community. It is crucial to study the efficacy of treatment provided to combat veterans and the success of that treatment over extended periods. By offering the most effective and long-lasting treatment, we can minimise the impact of PTSD on others, as well as on the veterans themselves.

In recent years, significant work has been done in the field of psychology regarding PTSD: the latest advancements in research focus on diagnosing and treating the disorder. The diagnostic criteria for PTSD have changed, and there is now a wide array of treatment options available. Studying PTSD and the effectiveness of treatment is pertinent to the field of psychology because, at any given time, over 12% of service members will develop PTSD (Murphy & Smith, 2018). The purpose of this literature review is to examine the effectiveness of treatments for PTSD in combat veterans. This examination will help determine the best treatments, why some therapies work as opposed to others, why certain individuals are predisposed to PTSD, and long-term treatment options that will enhance the quality of life for those suffering from PTSD.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature search strategy

This literature review utilised single-study, evidence-based research articles. Only articles published within the last 13 years were included to ensure the most current data was used. Several keywords were employed in the search, including: "barriers", "combat", "comorbidity", "effective treatments", "efficacy of treatment", "interventions", "posttraumatic stress disorder/post-traumatic stress disorder", "trauma". The databases used to search for relevant articles included EBSCOhost, ProQuest, PsycINFO, and ScienceDirect.

Neurobiology of PTSD

Posttraumatic stress disorder (PTSD) is a mental disorder resulting from exposure to a traumatic episode or event. PTSD significantly impacts how a person functions in everyday life and various environments. Over 2 million military personnel in the United States have been exposed to combat,

with the prevalence of PTSD exceeding 20% among military veterans (Averill et al., 2021; Chavez-Valdez et al., 2019).

An important neurobiological component of PTSD is the overgeneralisation of negative context. Levy-Gigi et al. (2015) examined the correlation between hippocampal volume and overgeneralisation in individuals with and without PTSD. While past researchers have studied hippocampal volume in individuals with PTSD, its functionality has never been explored. The participants included 26 combat-exposed veterans with PTSD and 22 combat veterans without PTSD. Data was collected through MRI scans, brain imaging, the Trauma and Life-Event Self-Report Inventory, the Hamilton Depression Scale, and the Wechsler Abbreviated Scale of Intelligence. The data was analyzed using SPSS software and Kolmogorov-Smirnov.

The results revealed that hippocampal volume was reduced in individuals with PTSD, contributing to the overgeneralisation of negative content. Hippocampal volume may predict an individual's susceptibility to PTSD. Additional research is needed to determine if individuals with reduced hippocampal volume are at risk for developing PTSD by testing them before they experience traumatic events (Levy-Gigi et al., 2015). The brain plays a vital role in PTSD, influencing not only cognitive processes but also neural processes.

Another important neurobiological impact of PTSD is brain function activity. Yan et al. (2013) investigated the extent of spontaneous brain activity in combat veterans. Little is understood about whether abnormal brain activity correlates with neural processes independent of environmental influences. The participants included 104 male combat veterans (ages 20 to 60 years) with and without PTSD. The sample was divided into two groups of 52 participants, matched by age and ethnicity. Data was collected using the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale, the PTSD Checklist, the Beck Depression Index, and several self-report measures. The Analysis of Functional NeuroImages software, a Siemens 3 T Trio scanner, and anatomical images were also used to collect data. Data was analyzed through regression analysis and an independent two-sample t-test.

The findings suggested that combat veterans experience significant increases in spontaneous brain activity. Future researchers should investigate whether the neural activity identified in this study could predict PTSD. This study also enhances the understanding of the neural characteristics of PTSD (Yan et al., 2013).

In addition to spontaneous brain activity, neurobiological indicators associated with PTSD include impulse control issues. Sadeh et al. (2015) examined changes in the brain and their connection to inhibition and impulsivity. The neurobiology of PTSD and its inhibitory malfunctions remain poorly understood. The participants consisted of 189 combat-exposed veterans (ages 19–62 years) with severe PTSD and depression. Data was collected from a series of self-report measures, clinical interviews—including the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale and the GNG task—MRI scans, and neuropsychological tests. Data was analyzed using morphometric processing, fMRI processing, descriptive statistics, and FreeSurfer. A lack of impulse control was found to be associated with PTSD, unusual brain changes, and cortical thinning. These behaviors could also result from external factors or environmental influences during combat. Future researchers should assess the destructive behaviors often linked to PTSD. The findings from this study provide insights into the loss of the brain's structural integrity and how it affects individual behavior and thinking (Sadeh et al., 2015). Another important factor in understanding PTSD is reduced cortical thickness. Averill et al. (2021) explored the impact of combat exposure on cortical thickness, extending findings from Sadeh et al. (2015). Previous studies have not examined how combat stressors affect neural integrity, although combat exposure is known to be a pathogenic stressor. The participants included 21 combat veterans diagnosed with PTSD and 20 combat veterans without PTSD (ages 18 to 50 years). Data was collected using self-report questionnaires: the Combat Exposure Scale, which assessed combat and wartime stress; the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire, which evaluated childhood abuse and neglect; and the Beck Depression Inventory-Second Edition, which measured depressive symptoms. The Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale distinguished between PTSD and non-PTSD diagnoses. Magnetic Resonance Imaging was utilised to examine cortical thickness. Data was analyzed using t-tests,

general linear models, Monte Carlo simulations, and FreeSurfer's Query, Design, Estimate, Contrast application (Averill et al., 2021).

The results showed a positive correlation between combat exposure and cortical thickness in the prefrontal and superior temporal regions. In other words, combat exposure is linked to poor cognitive performance and aggression. Future researchers should investigate whether significant past stress or trauma may account for cortical thickening. Differences between men and women regarding cortical thickening should also be explored (Averill et al., 2021).

While anyone can develop PTSD, servicemen and women who have experienced combat are disproportionately affected. Given the significant impact of PTSD, understanding its neurobiological effects and potential treatments is crucial. Combat veterans with PTSD show reduced hippocampal volume, which contributes to the overgeneralisation of negative thoughts and beliefs (Levy-Gigi et al., 2015). Veterans also exhibit abnormal brain changes linked to impulsivity (Sadeh et al., 2015), increased spontaneous brain activity (Yan et al., 2013), and an association between combat exposure and cortical thickness (Averill et al., 2021). With a clearer understanding of PTSD, it becomes essential to explore the available treatment options.

Understanding PTSD in combat veterans

PTSD in combat veterans is often linked to exposure to trauma in warfare, including threats to life, injury, and witnessing death. Symptoms encompass flashbacks, hypervigilance, sleep disturbances, and emotional numbness. Importantly, studies reveal that the effects of PTSD extend beyond the individual, significantly impacting family dynamics, employment, and community integration.

Treatment models

A common limitation across PTSD treatment studies is the dependence on small sample sizes and limited follow-up periods, undermining the generalisability of findings. A variety of treatments have been developed, including trauma-focused cognitive behavioural therapy (CBT), eye movement desensitisation and reprocessing (EMDR), Prolonged Exposure Therapy, and emerging web-based interventions. These approaches generally yield positive short-term results.

However, critical limitations are frequently overlooked. Many studies include small, homogeneous samples and short follow-up durations. For example, their pilot study on web-based interventions demonstrates the effectiveness of these approaches. Brief et al. (2013) reported promising outcomes but failed to address long-term relapse rates and lacked diversity in participant demographics. The absence of gender, racial, and ethnic diversity in their study restricts the applicability of the findings to broader veteran populations. This is particularly concerning given that female, Black, and Latino veterans face unique cultural and systemic barriers to accessing and responding to treatment, factors that can profoundly influence both engagement and outcomes. This raises issues about generalisability, especially for minority veterans who encounter systemic barriers to care.

Types of treatment

Numerous treatments are available to minimise PTSD symptoms. To address self-stigma, web-based, self-managed treatments are frequently utilised for PTSD and related alcohol issues (Brief et al., 2018). Other promising treatments include Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (MBCT) (King et al., 2013) and Group-Based Exposure Therapy (GBET) (Ready et al., 2012). Additionally, complementary and alternative medicines are used to address PTSD (Libby et al., 2013).

Brief et al. (2013) explored the effectiveness of a new self-managed web treatment programme named VetChange, which aimed to reduce alcohol consumption and PTSD symptoms in combat veterans. There was a limited selection of evidence-based treatments for veterans facing both alcohol abuse and PTSD. The study involved 600 combat veterans (ages 18 to 65) recruited via social media to participate in a randomised clinical trial. Participants were divided into two groups: one consisting of

404 individuals who received immediate intervention and another of 196 who received delayed intervention. Data was gathered through various self-report measures, such as the Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test to assess alcohol use and related issues, the Quick Drink Screen to gauge alcohol consumption over the last 30 days, and the Short Inventory of Problems to evaluate alcohol-related concerns. The Combat Experiences Scale from the Deployment Risk and Resilience Inventory measured combat exposure, while the PTSD Checklist-5 assessed PTSD symptoms.

The results demonstrated that VetChange was effective in reducing or eliminating alcohol consumption and alleviating PTSD symptoms. This study contributes to understanding the effectiveness of web-based interventions and proposes enhancements for similar treatments. Future researchers should consider participant attrition and incorporate longer follow-up periods beyond the 3-month mark (Brief et al., 2013).

With the notion of web-based treatments as a viable option for PTSD, Brief et al. (2018) investigated treatment within a more severely affected population. They assessed the effectiveness of online treatments for individuals with significant PTSD and combat exposure. Limited research has been conducted to compare patient characteristics with the effectiveness of web-based therapies. The study involved 523 combat-exposed veterans (ages 18 to 65) who completed self-report questionnaires. The Quick Drinking Screen was utilised to assess the volume of alcohol consumed, while the Short Inventory of Problems measured alcohol-related issues. The Combat Experiences Scale from the Deployment Risk and Resilience Inventory monitored combat exposure, and the PTSD Checklist assessed PTSD symptoms. Data analysis included natural log transformation, square root transformation, multivariable linear regression models, and longitudinal analyses. Results showed that participants with more severe symptoms of PTSD and combat exposure faced significant alcohol issues. Even those with the most severe PTSD and combat exposure symptoms benefited greatly from web-based treatments. Thus, future web-based PTSD and alcohol treatments can include populations with more severe cases. Future researchers should involve more minorities and younger veterans, as those demographics were underrepresented in this study and could influence the outcome of the collected data. Additionally, researchers should implement a longer follow-up period to ensure positive outcomes over time, as this study only included a 3-month follow-up period (Brief et al., 2018). Besides web-based treatments, research has shown that group-based therapy is an effective option. Ready et al. (2012) examined the effectiveness of GBET on combat veterans diagnosed with PTSD and depression. Previous research has investigated various types of treatments for PTSD, but the effectiveness of those treatments remains poorly established. The participants included 30 combat veterans diagnosed with severe PTSD (ages 21 to 65) who were referred by the Atlanta Veterans Affairs General Mental Health Clinic. Data was collected using the PTSD Checklist, which assessed the severity of PTSD symptoms, the Beck Depression Inventory-II, which evaluated depression symptoms and a follow-up assessment after Group-Based Exposure Therapy.

The data was analyzed using Bonferroni corrections, Jacobsen and Truax's Reliable Change Index, and measures of analysis of covariance. The results indicated that GBET significantly reduced or eliminated both PTSD and depressive symptoms. The findings from this research are vital in providing an effective treatment that addresses both depression and PTSD in an intensive format. GBET includes not only treatment but also psychosocial skills training and psychological education, reducing the need for multiple interventions. Future researchers should include a comparison group and ensure a confirmed PTSD diagnosis (Ready et al., 2012).

In a subsequent study, King et al. (2013) investigated the effectiveness of MBCT in a group setting for combat PTSD by presenting initial data. MBCT has been researched and shown to be effective in treating depression, but studies on its effectiveness for anxiety disorders are limited. The participants consisted of 37 combat veterans seeking treatment for PTSD. Data collection involved semi-structured interviews, the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale, the PTSD Diagnostic Scale, and the Post-Traumatic Cognitions Inventory. The data was analysed using various methods, including t-tests, chi-squared analyses, and repeated-measures analyses of variance.

The results demonstrated that MBCT is a brief and effective treatment for PTSD. The duration of MBCT is shorter compared to other treatments commonly used for chronic PTSD, yet it is comparable in effectiveness to those treatments. Future researchers should further explore MBCT in combat PTSD using larger sample sizes (King et al., 2013).

Another aspect of PTSD treatment related to mindfulness-based approaches is hyperarousal. Doron-Lamarca et al. (2015) investigated changes in PTSD symptoms over time through temporal associations. The participants included 34 combat veterans diagnosed with combat PTSD. Several factors were measured, including the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale to confirm the PTSD diagnosis and the PTSD Checklist-Military Version to assess the severity of PTSD symptoms. Data analysis employed descriptive statistics and multilevel regression.

The results showed that hyperarousal was the only predictor of changes in other symptom clusters. Treatment specifically aimed at hyperarousal would be beneficial in addressing ongoing PTSD. Future research is needed to assess a larger population without retrospective recall of PTSD symptoms (Doron-Lamarca et al., 2015).

Other types of treatments available for PTSD include exposure-based and rescripting-based imagery, along with trauma-focused psychotherapy. Langkaas et al. (2017) investigated whether imagery rescripting (IR) is more effective than prolonged exposure (PE) for treating PTSD. Only one previous study had compared IR and PE, but it did not address the role of non-fear emotions. The participants consisted of 65 patients diagnosed with PTSD (38 women, 27 men, age range 18 to 67 years). Data was collected from the PTSD Symptom Scale Interview, the Beck Depression Inventory-II, the WHOQOL-BREF, and the Anger Expression Scale. The Trauma-Related Shame Inventory, the MINI International Neuropsychiatric Interview, and the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Axis II were also used to gather data. The data was analyzed using linear mixed models and normative reporting.

The results indicated that both treatments effectively reduced PTSD symptoms, with no significant difference between them. The findings suggested that both PE and IR can be effectively used to treat PTSD, whereas they were once primarily designed to address excessive fear. Future research should include similar testing but with untreated controls and, preferably, in an outpatient setting (Langkaas et al., 2017). Alternative therapies for treating excessive fear associated with PTSD include brief eclectic psychotherapy and eye movement desensitisation and reprocessing therapy. Nijdam et al. (2018) investigated posttraumatic growth in response to these therapies. Previous researchers have mainly focused on negative psychopathological outcomes. Participants in this randomised controlled trial included 116 individuals diagnosed with PTSD following at least one nonspecific traumatic event. Data was collected using the Posttraumatic Growth Inventory to assess positive outcomes, the Structured Interview for PTSD and the Impact of Event Scale-Revised to measure PTSD symptom severity, the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Disorders to evaluate comorbid psychiatric diagnoses, and the Depression Scale of the Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale to assess depressive symptoms. The data was analyzed using SPSS Statistics 23, t-tests, Mann-Whitney U tests, and linear mixed models. The findings indicated an increase in posttraumatic growth following trauma-focused therapy. Posttraumatic growth represents an additional benefit of PTSD treatment. Future researchers should validate self-reported growth against changes in various functional areas (Nijdam et al., 2018). Another increasingly popular treatment method is complementary and alternative medicine (CAM). Libby et al. (2013) investigated the usage and effectiveness of CAM therapies among individuals with PTSD. Limited research has been conducted to examine the effectiveness of self-administered versus provider-based CAM. Participants included 599 individuals diagnosed with PTSD (ages 18 to 44 years) selected through probability sampling. Data was collected through a series of surveys and interviews, along with analysis from Collaborative Psychiatric Epidemiology surveys and the National Comorbidity Survey-Replication. The data was analysed using descriptive statistics, SAS 9.1, Taylor Series Linearization procedures, SUDAAN 9.0, and Wald chi-square tests. The findings revealed widespread usage of CAM therapies among individuals with PTSD, comparable to traditional mental health care. This study aids care providers in enhancing the benefits and mitigating the risks of CAM approaches by discussing CAM options with their patients. Future researchers should continue to explore the efficacy of CAM therapies (Libby et

al., 2013). With the various treatment methods available, the delivery format is evolving to reach more veterans. Web-based interventions have proven effective in reducing alcohol consumption and PTSD symptoms (Brief et al., 2013). Group-based therapies have also significantly reduced PTSD and depression symptoms (King et al., 2013; Ready et al., 2012). Trauma-focused therapy has been shown to increase posttraumatic growth in veterans (Nijdam et al., 2018). Finally, CAM therapy is growing in popularity and is utilised as much as traditional mental health care (Libby et al., 2013). With numerous treatment options available for veterans, many have proven effective. While many of the cited interventions report promising short-term results, the lack of long-term follow-up and underrepresentation of diverse veteran populations limit their generalisability. In particular, studies such as Brief et al. (2013) and Ready et al. (2012) rely heavily on self-report measures and small samples, raising questions about their findings and broader applicability.

Efficacy of treatment

With the rising number of treatments for PTSD, it is crucial to understand their effectiveness and how they alleviate symptoms. Trauma Management Therapy effectively reduces PTSD symptoms, depression, and anger; it is intensive, rapid, and delivered in a group format (Beidel et al., 2017). Cognitive Behavioral Treatment has also proven effective for PTSD and sleep disturbances (Margolies et al., 2013). Even with the most effective treatments, studies indicate that the patient's outcome expectancy plays an essential role in treatment efficacy (Price et al., 2015).

Combat veterans experience poorer treatment outcomes than their civilian counterparts. Understanding treatment effectiveness requires comprehending treatment responses. Murphy and Smith (2018) examined the treatment response in veterans with PTSD. Researchers remain uncertain about why veterans with PTSD do not respond well to treatment. The participants included 960 military veterans diagnosed with PTSD who were prescribed and taking psychiatric medication. Data was collected through a sociodemographic questionnaire; the Impact of Event Scale-Revised measured PTSD symptoms, the Patient Health Questionnaire assessed depression, anger was evaluated using the Dimensions of Anger Reactions, an anxiety disorder questionnaire gauged anxiety, the Work and Social Adjustment Scale examined functional impairment, and the Alcohol Use Disorders Identification Test measured alcohol misuse. Data was analysed using Mplus with FIML implemented to address missing data, as well as a latent growth model and latent class growth analysis.

The results revealed that most veterans showed improvement in the severity of PTSD symptoms after one year of treatment, but a significant number did not respond to treatment at all. Experiencing combat, combined with depression and anxiety, increased the likelihood of resistance to treatment. It is crucial to triage returning combat veterans and offer treatments tailored to the severity of their PTSD symptoms. A more accurate assessment of PTSD severity would be beneficial for delivering the most effective care, in addition to tailored interventions based on symptom severity (Murphy & Smith, 2018).

Several effective treatments reduce PTSD symptoms. Jackson et al. (2019) examined the effectiveness of an evidence-based treatment, Group Skills Training in Affective and Interpersonal Regulation (STAIR). However, no studies have evaluated the effectiveness of intensive outpatient formats for this population. Participants included 39 veterans (aged 25 to 68 years) diagnosed with PTSD. Data was collected using self-report questionnaires; the Post-traumatic Stress Checklist evaluated PTSD symptoms (pre-treatment and post-treatment), and the Brief Symptom Inventory measured psychological distress. Data was analyzed using chi-square, t-tests, Cohen's d, and SAS PROC MIXED. The results revealed that while this treatment method was effective, male veterans benefited more from this intervention than female veterans. Respondents reported that participating in a mixed-gender group helped challenge their trauma-based interpersonal beliefs. Future researchers should examine the benefits and limitations of mixed-gender therapy groups and longitudinal studies for this treatment approach (Jackson et al., 2019).

An earlier study by Beidel et al. (2017) explored the effectiveness of Trauma Management Therapy among combat veterans when delivered in an intensive format. Previous research on PTSD treatment for combat veterans showed no significant treatment benefits. The participants included 122 combat veterans, of whom 100 completed the treatment program. Data was collected using various measures, including the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale, PTSD Checklist-Military Version, and Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV, Quality of Life Inventory, Health-Related Functioning: Medical Outcome Study Short Form, and the Behavior Rating Inventory of Executive Function. Additionally, self-monitoring was utilised, along with the Trauma-Related Guilt Inventory, Clinical Global Impressions Scale, and Hamilton Rating Scale for Depression, and the Clinician-Administered Rating Form of Functional Indicators. The data was analysed using intent-to-treat analysis, t-tests, the Wilcoxon Signed Rank Test, and confirmatory factor analysis

The findings indicated that the method of delivering TMT treatment did not influence the outcome, yet it remains a practical, safe, and effective way to provide intensive outpatient PTSD treatment. This study offers an alternative method of treatment delivery that preserves its effectiveness. Future researchers should evaluate treatment effectiveness over a longer duration (Beidel et al., 2017).

Another crucial aspect of addressing PTSD involves tackling symptoms associated with depression, such as insomnia and nightmares, which exacerbate PTSD symptomology. Margolies et al. (2013) investigated the effectiveness of cognitive-behavioral therapy combined with imagery rehearsal therapy. Little research has focused on therapies that primarily target sleep disturbances in veterans with PTSD. The participants comprised 40 combat veterans (mean age 37.7) with documented PTSD and sleep disturbances, randomly assigned to two groups: a treatment group and a waitlist control group. Data was collected through various measures, including a sleep diary documenting sleep time, actigraphy recording activity during sleep, and the self-report Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index assessing sleep quality over the previous 30 days. The Insomnia Severity Index rated sleep, the Dysfunctional Beliefs and Attitudes About Sleep Scale measured sleep-related beliefs, and the PTSD Symptom Scale-Self Report assessed the frequency of PTSD symptoms. The Patient Health Questionnaire-9 evaluated depression symptoms and the Profile of Mood States examined mood disturbances. Data was analyzed using intent-to-treat analyses, multivariate analysis of variance, paired-samples t-tests, and partial eta squared.

The results demonstrated that 60% of participants who utilised CBT with IRT experienced improved sleep, mood, depression, and PTSD symptoms. Based on this study, this therapy is considered a viable treatment option; however, due to its intensive nature, a stepped care approach afterward would be advantageous. Future researchers should explore whether CBT and IRT can be integrated with evidence-based PTSD treatments (Margolies et al., 2013).

In any effective treatment, the most crucial factor is the veteran's perception of how effective the treatment will be. Price et al. (2015) explored the relationship between outcome expectancy and improved outcomes, noting a lack of research in this area regarding PTSD. The study involved 116 combat veterans (ages 23 to 55) diagnosed with PTSD. Data was gathered through clinician-rated, self-report, and biological measures, as well as salivary cortisol samples. The Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale diagnosed PTSD, the Clinician Global Impressions assessed clinical improvements and severity of illness, and the Outcomes Expectations measure gauged treatment expectations. The PTSD Symptom Scale measured PTSD symptoms, while the Beck Depression Inventory II evaluated depression, and the State Trait Anxiety Inventory assessed anxiety. The Clinical Global Impression Self-Report measured overall psychopathology, and the Trauma-Potentiated Startle measured the startle reflex. The data was analysed using a two-level piecewise model, random effects, dummy-coded variables, and regressions.

The findings revealed a positive correlation between outcome expectancy and treatment success. Clinicians should assess their patients' outcome expectations and strive to positively enhance those expectations throughout treatment to foster better outcomes and treatment effectiveness. Future researchers should include more female samples and replicate the study without medication (Price et al., 2015).

Treatment options for veterans cannot be uniform; they must be tailored to fit each patient's unique needs and severity of symptoms. Trauma Management Therapy is an effective treatment delivery method, even though it did not influence outcomes (Beidel et al., 2017). The STAIR group treatment, while effective, proved more beneficial for men than for women (Jackson et al., 2019). Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy used alongside Imagery Rehearsal Therapy effectively reduced PTSD-related symptoms (Margolies et al., 2013). Despite the effectiveness of various treatments, a significant number of veterans still do not respond adequately (Murphy & Smith, 2018), and outcome expectancy remains the key factor in treatment effectiveness, positively correlating with treatment success. Many veterans with PTSD also face additional challenges and barriers to treatment in other areas.

Emerging approaches and limitations

Complementary and alternative therapies such as yoga, meditation, and equine therapy are gaining popularity. These methods aim to treat the whole person and promote sustained recovery. However, empirical support remains limited, and many studies do not disaggregate data by race or gender, making it difficult to assess the applicability of findings across the diverse veteran population.

Barriers to treatment

Barriers to care are substantial and include stigma, distrust of institutions, logistical challenges, and perceived ineffectiveness of treatment. These issues disproportionately affect female and minority veterans, who are underrepresented in clinical trials and often excluded from targeted outreach.

One significant barrier to treatment is the self-stigma that combat veterans feel about themselves and their need for treatment. Mittal et al. (2013) investigated the stigmas associated with PTSD that create a barrier for combat veterans seeking treatment. There is limited information known about the stigmas associated with PTSD, and these stigmas impact treatment. Sixteen veterans diagnosed with combat-related PTSD participated in the study. Data was collected using an interview guide to gain an understanding of attitudes toward PTSD. The data was analyzed using both deductive and inductive approaches and independent coding, employing an iterative process to analyse transcribed data.

The results revealed that combat veterans are reluctant to seek treatment due to fear of how they will be viewed, potential labels, and their self-stigma. The lack of support in the veteran's environment increases self-stigma and behaviors that prevent veterans from seeking treatment. Peer groups and outreach are essential for early intervention. Future researchers should encompass a larger study, including more female veterans (Mittal et al., 2013).

Another study published in 2013 aimed to identify additional barriers that might hinder treatment. Stecker et al. (2013) found that many veterans did not fully understand the treatment options available to them, or they did not feel emotionally ready for treatment. The researchers examined barriers to treatment-seeking in combat veterans. Despite the rising number of veterans diagnosed with PTSD, many are not receiving treatment. The study included 143 military personnel with combat-related PTSD (age range 19 to 50 years). Data was collected utilising the Mini-International Neuropsychiatric Interview-PTSD to initially screen for PTSD, the PTSD Checklist-Military Version, which assessed PTSD symptom severity, and the Physician's Health Questionnaire, which measured major depressive disorder. Participants were asked about their beliefs regarding seeking treatment for PTSD. The data was analyzed using standard thematic analysis.

The results indicated that most veterans not receiving treatment were concerned about the treatment itself and/or unsure if they were ready emotionally. This study highlighted areas for improving delivery methods aimed at reducing the barriers to PTSD treatments for combat veterans. This research identifies potential improvements in interventions to eliminate barriers to treatment (Stecker et al., 2013).

In addition to the lack of knowledge about PTSD treatments and the emotional readiness for treatment, another barrier is alcohol use. Possemato et al. (2015) investigated the relationship between alcohol use and PTSD. There was insufficient evidence supporting current models attempting to explain the connection between alcohol use and PTSD, including self-medication. Participants in this study included 143 combat veterans (126 males, 17 females, mean age of 30 years). Data was collected through mixed-methods research. The Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale was used to assess PTSD symptoms, the Substance Use Disorders Module of the Structured Clinical Interview evaluated alcohol use disorder, the Timeline Follow-Back assessed daily alcohol consumption and the frequency of other drug use, and the Ecological Momentary Assessment monitored alcohol use and PTSD symptoms. Self-report measures included the Coping Responses Inventory, which evaluated coping styles, the Situational Confidence Questionnaire assessing self-efficacy, and a sociodemographic and military background questionnaire. The data was analyzed using generalised linear mixed models.

The results revealed that avoidance coping correlated with an increase in PTSD symptoms and alcohol consumption. The findings also indicated that self-efficacy and PTSD symptoms had a weaker relationship with drinking. Reducing avoidance coping interventions for PTSD could help veterans decrease their alcohol consumption, while interventions that enhance self-efficacy to control alcohol use might lower drinking levels even if PTSD symptoms escalate. Future researchers should employ different assessment schedules and evaluate sleep to strengthen the methodology (Possemato et al., 2015).

Possemato also participated in a later study to expand on the findings from his previous research. Possemato et al. (2017) examined alcohol consumption and its effects on PTSD symptoms. Limited research has explored the long-term effects of PTSD and alcohol consumption in individuals with comorbid PTSD and AUD. The participants included 112 recent combat veterans with PTSD (average age 30 years). Researchers utilised qualitative methods, including interviews and self-report measures, to assess PTSD symptoms, AUD symptoms, coping skills, depression symptoms, and alcohol use. The assessments included the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale, the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV, the Longitudinal Interview Follow-up Evaluation, the Timeline Followback, the Coping Responses Inventory, and the Center for Epidemiologic Studies Depression Scale. The statistical analyses employed to analyse the data included multinomial logistic regression and latent class growth mixture modelling.

The findings suggested no correlation in fluctuations between alcohol use and PTSD symptoms over an extended period. Results from this study were inconsistent with earlier research that investigated the course of comorbid PTSD and AUD. Future researchers would benefit from a longer follow-up period (Possemato et al., 2017).

In addition to alcohol use, which creates barriers to treatment, cannabis use does as well. Bujarski et al. (2016) examined the current understanding of barriers that cannabis use disorders present to effective treatment. There is a lack of evidence regarding effective integrated treatment for individuals diagnosed with PTSD and CUD. Participants included key personnel from 39 treatment programs. It is vital to interview clinicians providing services to veterans to understand how their beliefs and knowledge about CUD impact treatment delivery and effectiveness. These participants were interviewed to assess clinicians' beliefs regarding four areas: knowledge about CUD, attitudes about CUD, knowledge and treatment information regarding co-occurring CUD and PTSD, and perceptions and barriers among veterans seeking treatment for CUD and PTSD. Data was collected through surveys and semi-structured interviews. The researchers coded the data using SPSS v.20 and NVivo.

Results revealed opportunities for training and education focused on cannabis use disorders for clinicians. Clinician beliefs about specific populations can also create barriers to treatment. Clinician behaviors can foster either a supportive or detrimental environment for veterans, directly influencing their attitudes and behaviors toward treatment. This study aids clinicians in diagnosing and treating veterans with PTSD and CUD and compels them to confront any misconceptions they may hold.

Future research is needed to interview the veterans themselves to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of patient factors (Bujarski et al., 2016).

Research conducted by Norrholm et al. (2016) aimed to understand the brain's role in barriers to treatment. Norrholm et al. (2016) examined psychophysiological and cortisol responses as predictors of treatment efficacy in individuals undergoing virtual reality exposure therapy. Research discussing predictive biomarkers of PTSD treatment effectiveness is scarce. The participants consisted of 50 combat veterans (age range 23 to 55 years) who were randomly assigned. Several measures were used to collect data, including clinical assessments, psychophysiological assessments, cortisol assays, and six sessions of virtual reality exposure therapy. The Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale was used to assess symptom severity, the Mini International Neuropsychiatric Interview assessed for comorbid diagnoses, the PTSD Symptom Scale, and the Childhood Trauma Questionnaire assessed trauma history. The data was analyzed using repeated measures analysis of variance, linear regression analyses, and SPSS 20.0.

Results indicated that higher psychophysiological and cortisol responses correlated with greater PTSD severity over time. Increased cortisol reactivity was associated with a higher likelihood of unfavourable treatment outcomes. Psychophysiological assessments are beneficial for measuring treatment effectiveness throughout the therapeutic process (Norrholm et al., 2016).

Numerous variables can hinder successful treatment and lead to poorer outcomes in combat veterans. These factors must be considered when implementing any type of treatment. Veterans may create barriers to treatment by worrying about how others will view them if they seek help (Mittal et al., 2013) and believing they are not emotionally ready to accept treatment (Stecker et al., 2013). Clinicians often lack adequate training to address both PTSD and co-occurring disorders such as substance use (Bujarski et al., 2016). Alcohol use complicates treatment effectiveness (Possemato et al., 2015), but the correlation remains poorly understood (Possemato et al., 2017). Increased psychophysiological and cortisol responses are linked to higher PTSD severity and decrease treatment efficacy (Norrholm et al., 2016). Beyond treatment effectiveness, these issues also affect veterans in other aspects of their lives.

Impacts of PTSD

After battling on foreign lands, military veterans return to confront challenges on the home front, such as parenting stress (Tomassetti-Long et al., 2015), which affects their children and interpersonal conflicts that impact relationships with their significant others (Knobloch-Fedders et al., 2017). It has also been documented that reintegration stress is a factor in suicidal ideations for returning veterans (Haller et al., 2015).

One significant impact of PTSD on combat veterans is reintegration stress. Haller et al. (2015) investigated whether reintegration issues significantly increase suicidal ideations in combat veterans. While PTSD is known to be a major factor in suicidal ideation, no studies have examined the relationship between reintegration stress and suicidal ideation. The study included 232 combat veterans with a mean age of 33.63 years. Data was collected using various tools: the Military to Civilian Questionnaire assessed reintegration difficulty, the Patient Health Questionnaire measured depression and suicidal ideations, the Post Traumatic Stress Checklist-Specific evaluated PTSD symptoms, and the Alcohol Use Disorder Identification Test assessed alcohol consumption. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS, logistic regressions, and exploratory analyses.

The results indicated that reintegration issues significantly increased suicidal ideations in combat veterans, and the risk of suicidal ideation is higher in this population with alcohol misuse. While in combat, veterans are accustomed to detailed instructions and routines. Therefore, reintegration should be addressed in existing treatments for PTSD, with early assessments for reintegration issues and concerns to reduce the risk of suicide. Future researchers should examine whether current treatments effectively address reintegration stress and how to better manage these stressors (Haller et al., 2015).

Not only does reintegration stress increase suicidal ideations, but posttraumatic cognitions also play a critical role in suicidal ideations and PTSD. Horwitz et al. (2018) explored the associations between suicidal ideations and posttraumatic cognitions. Although there have been studies examining the relationship between PTSD and SI, the nature of that relationship remains unclear. The study involved 177 veterans (average age of 41.7) diagnosed with PTSD. Data was collected using various measures: the Posttraumatic Cognitions Inventory assessed negative cognitions, the PTSD Checklist for DSM-5 evaluated the severity of PTSD symptoms, and the Patient Health Questionnaire was used to assess suicidal ideations and depression severity. The data was analyzed using t-tests, chi-square analyses, SPSS version 22, correlations, binary logistic regression, and the Hosmer-Lemeshow tests.

The findings suggested that negative posttraumatic cognitions are important factors in the relationship between PTSD and SI. This helps us begin to learn and understand how posttraumatic cognitions impact suicidal ideations. Future researchers should extend this study to include suicidal behaviors and assess which posttraumatic cognitions affect suicidal behaviors (Horwitz et al., 2018). These posttraumatic cognitions also impact the veteran's interpersonal relationships and the interactions between the veteran and their significant other, causing distress for the significant other. Knobloch-Fedders et al. (2017) investigated the differences in behavior between service members with and without PTSD and their female counterparts. Only one previous study explored the interactions of couples directly affected by PTSD. The participants included two randomly assigned groups, with one group comprising 27 married and 5 unmarried couples dealing with PTSD, while the second group included 32 married couples not affected by PTSD. Several measures collected the data: the Clinician-Administered PTSD Scale gauged the existence of PTSD, the PTSD Checklist-Military Version differentiated between the PTSD and non-PTSD groups, and the Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV-TR Research Edition measured current psychopathology. The Marital Satisfaction Inventory-Revised assessed relationship quality, the Areas of Disagreement Questionnaire produced focuses for conflict discussions, and the Impact Message Inventory-Circumplex rated certain behaviors of the spouses. The data was analyzed using multilevel modeling, maximum likelihood estimation, and empirical distinguishability. The results revealed that couples with a partner with PTSD reported higher distress. There was no difference in income or length of marriage. Family treatment for PTSD would be beneficial to alleviate distress within the relationship. Additional research should examine maladaptive interactions and distinguish them from PTSD symptomology and related psychopathology (Knobloch-Fedders et al., 2017). Researchers in an earlier study examined parenting stress and its impact on the veteran's children. Tomassetti-Long et al. (2015) investigated the relationship between the symptoms of PTSD and hardiness as a predictor of parenting stress. Past research has examined the link between PTSD and parenting issues in male veterans but did not assess the role of hardiness as a predictor of parenting stress. The participants included 94 combat veterans (all male, mean age of 34.35 years) with children under the age of 13. Data was collected through a demographic questionnaire, the Dispositional Resilience Scale assessed hardiness, the Parenting Stress Index-Short Form measured parenting stress, and the Posttraumatic Stress Disorder Checklist-Military Version assessed PTSD related to military stress. Various statistical methods analyzed the data, including Pearson correlation, biserial correlations, and hierarchical multiple regression.

Results indicated that PTSD and hardiness were significant indicators of parenting stress in fathers. There is a need for interventions related to parenting for combat veterans, which will help reduce parental stress and dysfunction within the family. Future researchers should compare these findings with other populations, such as female veterans, and address other aspects of adjustment after deployment while exploring social supports (Tomassetti-Long et al., 2015). When veterans return, they face challenges related to reintegration stress, which can increase alcohol use and suicidal ideations among veterans (Haller et al., 2015). The difficulty of adjusting to life back home, compounded by PTSD, presents challenges of its own. Male veterans, in particular, struggle with their parenting roles (Tomassetti-Long et al., 2015) and interpersonal relationships, especially with their spouses, who report higher distress (Knobloch-Fedders et al., 2017). With a true understanding of how PTSD affects veterans, we can begin to not only treat PTSD but also address other ailments that contribute to increased PTSD symptoms.

DISCUSSION

This review examines the effectiveness of traditional and emerging treatments for post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) in combat veterans. While there is agreement that multiple evidence-based treatments exist, there is still a gap between the availability of these treatments and the recovery rates of veterans. Although cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and prolonged exposure (PE) are considered the gold standards, high dropout rates and persistent symptoms highlight the need for more individualised, holistic, and accessible approaches.

A key trend emerging from this review is the growing support for integrative treatment models. These models combine evidence-based psychotherapies with complementary interventions such as mindfulness, peer support, and service dog programs. These interventions address aspects of healing that extend beyond simple symptom reduction, including identity reconstruction, moral injury, and reintegration into civilian life—areas where traditional approaches often fall short. This trend reflects a shift from viewing PTSD solely as a disorder to understanding it as a complex life disruption that requires flexible, multidimensional care.

The increasing prominence of web-based interventions underscores a broader push for accessibility and scalability. While online cognitive processing therapy and telehealth programs reduce logistical barriers, their long-term impact on treatment adherence and the therapeutic alliance remains uncertain. There is a need to identify which veterans benefit most from these digital platforms and under what conditions. Furthermore, while these interventions can enhance access, they may not adequately address the embodied or relational aspects of trauma recovery.

One of the most pressing issues in this field is the disconnect between the abundance of clinical research and the lived experiences of veterans. Much of the literature treats combat veterans as a single group and overlooks differences related to gender, ethnicity, service era, and the nature of trauma exposure. Female and minority veterans remain underrepresented in clinical trials, which limits the generalisability of findings and contributes to inequities in care. There is an urgent need for a more intersectional approach to research, one that recognises the cultural, social, and structural dimensions of trauma and healing.

Additionally, a significant gap in the current literature is the lack of sustained follow-up in many studies. While some treatments demonstrate short-term effectiveness, PTSD is a chronic and relapsing condition for many veterans. Longitudinal studies are essential to understanding which interventions promote long-term recovery, resilience, and life satisfaction. The field would benefit from shifting its focus from merely reducing symptoms to supporting veterans in building meaningful, connected lives.

This literature synthesis suggests that there is no one-size-fits-all treatment for PTSD in combat veterans. The future lies in personalisation, cultural responsiveness, and integration. Researchers and clinicians must continue to advocate for approaches that are not only evidence-based but also informed by veterans, trauma-sensitive, and adaptable to various contexts.

IMPLICATIONS

With PTSD being a term that began to be used in the 1970s and its classification changing even more recently, there are many areas and implications for future research (Beidel et al., 2017). Recommendations for future research include a significant increase in studies that include female and minority veteran populations (Brief et al., 2018). Many studies focused on PTSD did not attempt to cross cultural and gender boundaries. Although these populations do not significantly participate in such studies, it is important to understand how PTSD and treatment affect them as well. Future research should examine evidence-based treatments and longitudinal studies on current treatments deemed effective (Possemato et al., 2017). This insight is needed to assess the effectiveness of treatment over an extended period.

Implications for future research should also focus on prevention methods, education, intervention, and treatment strategies. Veterans who have been in combat experience poorer treatment outcomes than civilians diagnosed with PTSD (Beidel et al., 2017). Understanding the various factors and barriers faced by this population will aid in creating the most effective treatment options.

Future studies must prioritise diversity in participant recruitment and address systemic inequities in mental health care access. Longitudinal studies with larger and more representative samples are essential. Researchers should also explore how cultural values and beliefs influence treatment-seeking behavior and outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Combat veterans face profound mental health challenges, and while current treatments for PTSD are beneficial for many, they are not universally effective. The lack of diversity in study populations and limited attention to long-term outcomes restrict our understanding of treatment efficacy across veteran subgroups. A shift toward more inclusive, culturally competent, and thoughtfully designed research is essential. Future directions must prioritise the real-world needs of diverse veterans, ensuring that treatment approaches are evidence-based and also equitable and sustainable.

Combat veterans' behavioral changes and mood alterations are directly related to their experiences in combat and the things they have witnessed there. The impact of PTSD affects veterans not only mentally but also physically and emotionally. PTSD also indirectly affects those closest to the veterans through secondary trauma (Zerach, 2015). PTSD is not something that will simply go away over time; rather, it is something that veterans will need to adjust to and cope with for the rest of their lives. It is important to study not only the efficacy of the treatment provided to combat veterans but also its success over a prolonged period. By providing the most effective and enduring treatment, the effects of PTSD on others, as well as on the veterans themselves, can be minimised. Combat veterans face unique and lasting psychological challenges. While current treatment modalities show promise, they are often limited in scope and generalisability. A broader, more inclusive, and culturally competent approach is needed. This includes refining evidence-based treatments and integrating holistic and faith-based interventions that resonate with the diverse lived experiences of veterans.

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